

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

D2.2 R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society

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R&I Lectures, Seminars, and Workshops on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society

Researchers organise lectures, seminars, or workshops connected to every secondment, typically one at host institution during secondment, one at home institution after reintegration.

Secondments and their accompanying deliverables take place within Work Package 2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society or Work Package 3: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment. At the onset of the secondment, in the Researcher Declaration Form, researchers indicate whether their research topic falls within WP2 or WP3. The following list contains lectures, seminars, or workshops that PRODIGEES researchers organised at their host institution and host institution within the theme of WP3. Presentations not included in the list are those related to PRODIGEES Network-Wide events: MGG PRODIGEES Authors Workshop (2022), MGG PRODIGEES Policy Labs (2024), MGG PRODIGEES Final Conference (2025), and the yearly Transnational Open Access Trainings (2020-2025). Secondment Activity Reports were to be submitted within 30 days after the end of the respective secondment; therefore, not all presentations at the home institution after the secondment have yet taken place.

Ayala Martinez, C. (2024, June 20): The Role of Digitalisation in South-South Cooperation.

Boeckle, J. & Reiners, W. (2022, May 10). Sustainability and international training for civil servants – local leadership.

Braun, M., Donath, L., Grimm, S., Hörbelt, S., Lampert, S., Reiners, W. & Wich, M. (2023, May 25). Sustainable digitalization in the Brazilian public sector.

Braun, M., Donath, L., Grimm, S., Hörbelt, S., Lampert, S., Reiners, W. & Wich, M. (2023, April 7). Sustainable digitalization in the civil service in Brazil.

Braun, M., Donath, L., Grimm, S., Hörbelt, S., Lampert, S., Reiners, W. & Wich, M. (2023, April 13). Sustainability and digitalization in the Brazil. Workshop with Enap and FGV/EBAPE.

Braun, M., Donath, L., Grimm, S., Hörbelt, S., Lampert, S., Reiners, W. & Wich, M. (2023, February 23). Sustainable digitalization in the Brazilian public sector. PRODIGEES research project.

Breuer, A. (2025, March 2-5). An interdisciplinary approach to identifying and countering root causes of digital disinformation: Evidence and international policy implications from the case of Brazil.

Breuer, A. (2025, February 25). Towards Information Integrity: A Holistic Framework for Understanding Disinformation and Polarization Across Different Country Contexts.

Breuer, A. (2024, March 12). To inform and misinform: the current situation of Brazil's information ecosystem. Webinar with Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Breuer, A. (2023, September 29). Digitalisation: Information Integrity and Information Pollution, IDOS PGP, Module III: Politics, governance and conflict.

Breuer, A. (2023, February 2). Conversatorio El acceso a la información y la apertura de datos: Beneficios y retos de la digitalización para la sociedad mexicana.

Breuer, A. (2023, February 2). Access to information and open data: Benefits and challenges for Mexican Society.

Čas, J. (2023, March 28). "Artificial intelligence" and social sustainability – approaches on the EU, global and Brazilian level.

Čas, J. (2023, January 25). "Artificial intelligence" and social sustainability – does ethics of artificial intelligence as a global challenge also need global answers?

Cavalcanti de Alcântara, R. (2024, October 22). Inhabiting body-territories in the datafied city.

Dang, V., (2023, September 27). Unpacking digital public infrastructure and digital common.

Dang, V., (2023, August 12). Unpacking digital public infrastructure.

Daulay, N., Fauri, A., Krisetya, B., Rachman, R., Widiyati, V. A. (2025, March 6): Joint presentation of PRODIGEES secondment research findings at CSIS.

Deneault, A. (2024, April 30). The PRODIGEES Project: Harnessing digitalization to track global transnational action.

Deneault, A. (2024, April 10). The PRODIGEES Project: Harnessing digitalization to track global transnational action.

Domínguez Virgen, J. C. (2022, June 14). Digital but still Unequal: The Challenges of Digitalisation for Emerging Powers - Mexico.

Domínguez Virgen, J. C. (2021, February 17). Digital but still unequal: the challenges of smart technologies from a comparative perspective. CIFE Executive Training Webinar, Centre international de formation européenne (CIFE), Nice, France.

Domínguez Virgen, J. C. (2020, November 12). Digital but still Unequal: The Challenges of Digitalisation for Emerging Powers - Mexico.

Federle, M. (2024, January 12). AI in the Pharmaceutical Industry.

Fichtner (2023, April 19). The Politics of Platform Governance: NetzDG, Democracy, and the Regulation of Content Moderation in Germany (and Brazil).

Fichtner (2023, June 26). Platform Regulation in Brazil – Marco Civil and PL2630.

Haegele, R. (2023, October 2). Workshop on qualitative research in Belém, Brazil during Amazon immersion expedition with FGV.

Haegele, R. (2024, February 22). Presentation of secondment findings at IDOS.

Hendytio, M. (2023, June 7). Effects of digital platforms on think tanks in Germany and Indonesia.

Hendytio, M. (2023, June 7). Think tanks digital communication for policy advocacy: exploring organizational and technical aspects.

Hendytio, Rafitrandi, Okthariza, Satria (2023, August 23). Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development (PRODIGEES) Seminar.

Heuwinkel, S. (2023, November 07). Presentation of secondment results at IDOS.

Krisetya, B. (2023, June 12). Digital Deception. Navigating the Global Response to Election Disinformation

Kumar, A. & Sanchez, F. J. P. (2022, September 13). PRODIGEES Roundtable.

Lynders, E. (2023, September 27). Potentials of Transnational Networks for Sustainability Transformations. The Case of the T20.

Lynders, E. (2022, November 24). Cooperation in global governance processes: Which paradigms do we follow? Which would we need?

Lynders, E. (2022, September 19). Paradigm shifts in environmental policies: the role of digital communication and knowledge exchange in the T20/G20 transnational policy community.

Lynders, E. (2022, September 4). Utopias of global cooperation. T20 Summit Side Event, Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), Kuta Selatan, Indonesia.

Okthariza, N. (2022, December 12). Discourse, ideas, and policy: the making of data protection policy in Indonesia.

Ordoñez, M. (2023, August 08). Explorando el nexo entre sustentabilidad y digitalización para fortalecer las capacidades de servidores públicos

Ordoñez, M. (2022, November 11). Virtual World Café: @ffective Voluntary Networks for Managing Global Governance.

Orihuela, I. (2024, July 2). Digitalisation and sustainable cities.

Rachman, R. (2025, January 30). Agents of Memory: Digitalisation of National Archives in Germany and Indonesia.

Rafliana, I. (2022, April 18). Traveling waves: the Indonesian tsunami warning system, BRIN PRW STS Webinar Series #1, Indonesia.

Rafliana, I. (2022, April 5). A safe ocean. 5th Ocean Decade Laboratory, Core event, UNESCO.

Reiners, W., Stewart, B., Kachelmann, M. (2024, April 28). MGG PRODIGEES Policy Labs: Digitalisation Towards Sustainable Development. Stellenbosch University, South Africa.

Reiners, W., Stewart, B., Kachelmann, M. (2024, October 29). PRODIGEES Secondments @ MGG Priorities and Planning Meeting. IDOS, Germany

Reiners, W. (2022, May 4). Digitalization and sustainable development – enabling narratives towards a green digital transformation. PRODIGEES Roundtable Discussion, Instituto Mora, Mexico.

Reiners, W. (2024, September 12): Artificial Intelligence and International Cooperation. JRF-Leitthementag KI, Aachen, Germany.

Reiners, W. (2024, December 12): Twin Transition in der Wirtschaft - Digitalisierung und Nachhaltigkeit zusammen denken. Netzwerkabend Wirtschaftsförderung Bonn, Germany.

Reiners, W. (2025, March 5): Digitalisation towards sustainable development. Instituto Mora, Mexico.

Sanchez, F. J. P. (2022, October 19). Society, Digitalisation, and Technological Change (SODICAT).

Satria, A. (2022, December 12). Understanding the threat of online radicalization in Indonesia: a 2018 snapshot.

Schneider, I. (2025, March 11). Business Models of Social Network platforms and the attention economy.

Schneider, I. (2024, March 27). Digital platform regulation and geopolitics – comparing perspectives on South Africa and Europe. Seminar with Stellenbosch University (SU), Stellenbosch, South Africa.

Schneider, I. (2023, January 24). Digital Sovereignty and data governance in times of geopolitical rivalry. Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (STIP) Forum Lecture Series, Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), New Delhi, India.

Schneider, I. (2022, March 23). Democratic governance of digital platforms and AI. Lecture with Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Schneider, I. (2021, November 25). Convergence and divergence in global data protection law. Panel discussion, King's College London & British Institute of International and Comparative Law (BIICL).

Schneider, I. (2020, March 3). Can digital platforms be regulated? A dialogue between the European Union and Mexico [Video]. Instituto Mora. YouTube.

Seeliger, L. (2025, January 16) Can Digitalisation Facilitate Ethical Water Governance in Complex Moral Contexts? A Case Study in Philippi Horticultural Area in Cape Town, South Africa.

Seeliger, L. (2024, December 17). Can Digitalisation Facilitate Ethical Sustainable Adaptive Collaborative Water Governance in Complex Moral Contexts? A Case Study on the Cape Flats Aquifer in the Philippi Horticultural Area in Cape Town, South Africa.

Stewart, B. (2023, May 5). Regional Open Science policy implementation: snapshots from science and technology regimes in Germany, Indonesia and Mexico.

Stewart, B. (2023, March 8). Socio-cultural and global challenge in organization.

Stewart, B. (2023, February 13). MGG Academy: Space for dialogue and cooperation.

Stewart, B. (2023, August 5). Field work in Indonesia and conducting a comparative discourse analysis.

Stewart, B. (2023 March 13). The State of Open Science in Indonesia: a preliminary analysis of digitalisation's impact on science regimes.

Stewart, B. (2021, November 16). Open Science: epistemologies, science policy implementation and digitalisation.

Stewart, B., Reiber, T. & Reiners, W. (2021, February 23-24). Digitainable Forum: Mindful use of Digitalization and Artificial Intelligence (D&AI) for the SDGs. Workshop with the Bonn Sustainability Alliance, Germany.

Valeriani, M. (2024, March 13). Co-Governance, Food and Communities: Investigating the role of Agri-based solutions in community building in Cape Town and Rome

Valeriani, M. (2024, April 18). Urban Food Systems between Innovation and Social Capital

Van der Westhuizen, J. (2024, June 22). 'Containing' Huawei: Comparing Brazil and South Africa's responses to US/China rivalry.

Van der Westhuizen, J. (2024, April 17). Huawei or the American way? Why Brazil and South Africa did not securitize 5G. Seminar with Stellenbosch University (SU), Stellenbosch, South Africa.